

OpenStreetMap as a multi-faceted research subject: the Academic Track at State of the Map 2021

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The OpenStreetMap (OSM) project has come a long way since its establishment in 2004, celebrating the uploading of its 100 millionth changeset on 25 February 2021 [1]. From a project led by a small group of mapping enthusiasts, OSM has grown into a comprehensive global geographic database produced by a global community of contributors, attracting attention from governments, NGOs, and recently, also global tech giants [2–4]. Along with this increasing interest from organizations, the academic community had also kindled an interest in OSM, with the first scientific paper in English focusing on OSM (i.e. having OpenStreetMap in its title) published as early as 2007, according to Google Scholar [5]. Since then, the study of OSM has grown into a distinct research stream and community, with 119 publications focusing on OSM in 2020 alone (again, per Google Scholar) [6].

Yet, OSM is a unique study object for the fields that frequently interact with it (mainly geo-information, computer science, geography and engineering [7]). It is not an abstract notion, distant from the researcher, but rather a constantly evolving multifaceted entity, defined not only by the data it contains but also by its users and the communities they form, in which researchers can take an active role. Accordingly, there is no one way to engage with OSM in research—one may use its data for other applications, study the quality of OSM data, the dynamics of data production or the behavior of contributors, and even produce tools and approaches for enriching the data and supporting data production [7]. Furthermore, OSM research may include direct and indirect interactions with the ever-growing OSM community, starting from engagement with data and ending with becoming an active member of the OSM Foundation and affiliated organizations, such as the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team (HOT). The Academic Track at the State of the Map conference is perhaps the most

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explicit example of such interactions. In the first three iterations of the Track (2018-2020), authors gave 40 talks, presented 18 posters, and enjoyed the opportunity to both receive direct feedback on their research from the larger OSM community, and interact with mappers. The nine studies included in the 4th edition of the Track, published in these proceedings, not only represent the variety of topics studied through OSM research, but also the full plethora of ways in which research and researchers choose to engage with OSM.

Two studies discuss use cases of OSM data. Will [8] provides a specific example, considering the development of a web-based interface for the purposes of allowing the specification of custom machine-readable language (MRL) queries which are executed on the Overpass service. These queries can be presented to the system as natural language questions such as "Which restaurants in Vienna are wheelchair-accessible?", hence increasing the accessibility of OSM data. Graux and Michel [9] adopt a broader perspective, investigating the usage and involvement of OSM in Horizon 2020 (H2020) projects funded by the European Union during the course of the H2020 programme. They analyse the presence of OSM and other geographic services in over 92,000 deliverables produced by over 8,000 projects and report that OSM has around 18,600 mentions across all deliverables. This suggests that the impact of OSM, which is traditionally difficult to measure, is substantial as the authors indicate that the projects involving OSM were funded with an overall budget of almost 4 billion euros of public money. In addition, such findings can inform the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) use of results, which is a requirement in H2020, for projects that have to do with OSM.

Other studies engage with OSM by investigating aspects of data quality. Juhász [10] proposes a new framework for evaluating the temporal accuracy of OSM with regards to the time it takes for mappers to incorporate real-world changes into the map. Through a case study using publicly available data from the Florida Department of Transportation (FDOT), Juhász is able to validate the approach by limiting the comparison to only highway features and successfully identifies the elapsed time between the known construction date and the update in OSM. The success of applying the framework to highway features gives hope to future development involving more authoritative data sources. Li & Anderson [11] propose a new method to detect vandalism in OSM through the concept of embeddings, e.g. an embedding contains users who have edited the same OSM feature. These embeddings are fed into a Gradient Boosting Decision Tree (GBDT) model which is trained using manually labeled OSM vandalism corpus for the name attribute of OSM features. Finally, Elias et al. [12] describe a plugin for the open source QGIS software offering spatio-temporal analysis of OSM data quality. The developed QGIS plugin allows for visualisation of the results of positional and thematic accuracy of OSM. In particular, the authors draw attention to the relevance of identifying aspects of quality and heterogeneity in OSM contributions for national mapping purposes.

These latter two studies show engagement that goes beyond inspecting OSM data: Elias et al. [12] focus is on providing direct utility to OSM users, editors, and researchers through the development of a new tool; Li & Anderson's model [11] is also used for an analysis distinguishing between different communities of editors by calculating the cosine similarity between the user embeddings, detecting new communities of non-corporate editors alongside the known communities from different corporations such as Apple or Facebook. Li and Anderson's work is joined by other user-centric studies, i.e. studies that focus on the dynamics of data production and editor behaviors. Veselovsky et al. [13] also

relate to the issue of corporate editors (CEs) employed by corporations such as Facebook, Apple, or Amazon, proposing a method to distinguish volunteer mappers from corporate mappers based on their editing behaviour in order to better analyse how the corporate editing activity which has emerged in the past years has influenced OSM. They use different machine learning algorithms and a new method for identifying the local time zone of each editor so that it can be compared to a “corporate editing signature” (marked by 8 hour workday and no activity on the weekend) to identify between 700 and 2000 additional corporate mappers. Sarkar & Anderson [14] offer an additional study of CEs, describing how they have influenced the editing interaction patterns between mappers in OSM from 2015 to 2019 using network analyses to represent editors as nodes and editing interactions between them as edges. The authors find that, despite CEs most often editing other CEs' work, there is still ample interaction between CEs and non-CEs with both of them editing each other's work. Finally, Owusu et al. [15] develop a classification schema to assess local data in OSM and its “fitness-for-purpose” for local OSM communities. Broken into two larger categories “core” and “specific”, the schema contains four levels that increase in specificity from mapping buildings, roads, or other easy-to-trace objects from satellite imagery objects to specific, localized knowledge. Utilizing the Osmose API, the authors categorize OSM editing into this schema over time and look for distinct patterns of evolution between the levels as time progresses. Quantitatively investigating these patterns across three different regions validates the schema and the framework's ability to characterize the evolution of OSM in each region with respect to when highly localized information was added to the map.

The issue of research providing utility for OSM, evident in [12] as discussed above, is also considered by Mooney and Galván [16], who address the question of what machine learning has ever done for OSM through a comprehensive literature review of approximately 50 research papers involving machine learning and OSM. The authors acknowledge that as a massive open geographic dataset, OSM is a tempting data source for machine learning researchers to investigate. By categorizing the types of machine learning papers involving OSM from quality-improvements to simple training datasets, the authors make clear the wide-range of OSM-related machine learning research. The authors warn researchers not to use machine learning simply for the sake of it as a popular new research technology, but to critically assess cases where machine learning provides a clear advantage to answering the research question.

Together, these 9 abstracts highlight three major themes in OSM research: data quality [10–12], the identity of contributors and the nature of their contributions [11, 13–15], and the use of new approaches and techniques such as machine learning within OSM data use and production [8, 16]. These themes, especially the latter two, are also the subject of intense and sometimes heated discussions within the OSM mapping community where questions and doubts regarding the utility and effects of CEs and machine-produced data are raised [4]. This stresses the importance of the interactions between the mapping and the research community, where the latter takes inspiration from the former while the former potentially enjoys the insights provided by the latter. Looking into the future and based on the experience from previous editions, we, the Academic Track Scientific Committee (see Figure 1) are certain that the Academic Track will continue to provide a welcomed stage supporting the development of these symbiotic relations. We wish to end this editorial by expressing our thanks to the authors who submitted their work to the Track and participated in it, to the State of the Map Working Group in charge of the organization, to all the

volunteers supporting the conference, and to the members of the OSM mapping and research communities who continuously work to improve OSM.

Figure 1. The Academic Track Scientific Committee during the online State of the Map 2021 conference.

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